

DOI: 10.31866/2617-2674.7.1.2024.302777

Oleksandr Bezruchko

*Doctor of Study of Art, PhD in Cinematographic Art, Television, Professor;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388
Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine*

**An in-depth study of children's images in works
of audiovisual art in the genre of horror**

Олександр Безручко

*доктор мистецтвознавства, професор;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388
Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв, Київ, Україна*

**Ґрунтовне дослідження дитячих образів
у творах аудіовізуального мистецтва в жанрі хоррор**

Баталіна Х. Ф. Дитина як втілення зла у фільмах жахів ХХ–ХХІ ст. : монографія. Київ : Вид. центр КУК, 2023. 216 с.

Баталіна, Х.Ф., 2023.
Дитина як втілення зла у фільмах жахів ХХ–ХХІ ст.
Київ: Видавничий центр КУК.

Batalina, Kh.F., 2023.
Dytyna yak vtilennia zla u filmakh zhakhiv XX-XXI st.
[The Child as the Embodiment of Evil in Horror Films of the XX-XXI Centuries]. Kyiv: KUK Publishing Center.

In 2023, the publishing centre of the Kyiv University of Culture published an interesting and perhaps unusual monograph by Khrystyna Batalina entitled *The Child as the Embodiment of Evil in Horror Films of the Twentieth and Twenty-First Centuries*. This scholar's study of children's images in the world and Ukrainian works of audiovisual art in the horror genre will help to reveal the deep aspects of human psychology and cultural stereotypes associated with the depiction of children in horror films as the embodiment of evil and its accidental carriers. While babies are mostly associated with innocence and safety, they can also sometimes represent threat and fear, particularly in the context of verbal and on-screen narratives.

The book contains eleven chapters: "Philosophical and Aesthetic Aspects of the Embodiment of the Defining Categories of Horror in Cinema" (Chapter 1), "Differentiating Horror Films of the Last Third of the Twentieth and the Beginning of the Twenty-First Century" (Chapter 2), "Ethno-cultural Foundations for Interpreting the Image of a Child as a Potential

Embodiment of Evil" (Chapter 3), "Mysterious Pregnancy as a Major Thematic Aspect of the 1960s" (Chapter 4), (Chapter 5), The Image of the Child Villain on the Soviet Screen (Chapter 6), The 1990s: Reasonable Cruelty (Chapter 7), Context and Interpretations of the 2000s: Child Victim and Child Manipulator" (Chapter 8), "Children from the Otherworld and Changes/Replacement of the Child's Essence" (Chapter 9), "A Scary Tale: Manifestations in the Genre Context of Horror" (Chapter 10), "Images of Children in Neo-Cuffs and Their Hollywood Rereading" (Chapter 11). The book is richly illustrated with stills from the films discussed in the text.

Genres in audiovisual art have been studied by many Ukrainian scholars, including H. Chmil (Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Cherkasova, 2020; Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Markhaichuk, 2020; Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Kupriichuk, 2021), V. Myslavskiy (Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Cherkasova, 2020; Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Markhaichuk, 2020; Myslavskiy and Bezruchko, 2021; Myslavskiy, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Kupriichuk, 2021),

O. Bezruchko et. al, 2020; Bezruchko and Kachmar, 2021; Bezruchko and Sukhin, 2023), I. Gavran (Bezruchko, Gavran, Hrabarchuk, Kostiuk, and Kot, 2020; Gavran, Levchenko and Pasichnyk, 2021), S. Kotliar (Kotliar, Mykhalov and Pereiaslavets, 2022), A. Medvedieva and Chernenko, 2021, O. Levchenko, Gavran, Levchenko and Pasichnyk, 2021; V. Mikhailov, Kotliar, Mykhalov and Pereiaslavets, 2022, G. Kot (Bezruchko, Gavran, Hrabarchuk, Kostiuk and Kot, 2020), N. Kostiuk (Bezruchko, Gavran, Hrabarchuk, Kostiuk and Kot, 2020, Batalina and Kostiuk, 2022), O. Hrabarchuk (Bezruchko, Gavran, Hrabarchuk, Kostiuk and Kot, 2020), V. Kupriichuk (Myslavskiyi, Chmil, Bezruchko and Kupriichuk, 2021), N. Markhaichuk (Myslavskiyi, Chmil, Bezruchko, and Markhaichuk, 2020), N. Cherkasova (Myslavskiyi, Chmil, Bezruchko and Cherkasova, 2020), and others.

However, no one in Ukraine, except for Kh. Batalina has studied the horror genre so thoroughly over the years. This can be confirmed by only a part of her publications listed below, which, as the titles suggest, are identical to the topic under study. Articles by Khrystyna Batalina (Kostiuk, Sichna) in Ukrainian professional Art Studies journals ("Researches of the Fine Arts: Theatre. Music. Cinema", "Almanac of Ukrainian Studies", "Academic Bulletin of Kyiv National Karpenko-Karyi University of Theatre, Cinema and Television", "Bulletin of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series: Audiovisual Art and Production" etc.): "On the History of the Creation and Interpretation of One of the Myths of Modern Cinematic 'Horror'" (Kostiuk, 2011b), "On the History of the Development of the Image of the Child in Horror Films" (Kostiuk, 2012a), "Prerequisites for the Emergence of the Image of the

Child as a Carrier of Evil in Contemporary Ukrainian and Russian Cinema" (Kostiuk, 2012d), "Mystical Motifs in the Works of Yuri Ilyenko" (Kostiuk, 2013d), "Screen Arts as a Means of Forming Modern Mythological Consciousness" (Kostiuk, 2013c), "Italian Horror of the 60s: Irrational Horror on the Screen" (Kostiuk, 2016c), and others.

Articles in foreign professional journals on art history and audiovisual art ("European philosophical and historical discourse"): "The Concept of Evil in the Image of a Child: Cinematic Variations in Horror Films" (January, 2017a), etc.

Chapters in collective monographs ("Cinema Studies, Cultural Studies and Art Studies (Social and Communication Aspect)", "Actual Issues of Screen Creativity", "Scientific and Practical Research on the Development of the Creative Process in Various Art Forms (Cinema, Television, Theatre, Media)", "Genesis of Ideas and Dynamics of Screen Arts Development", "Art Studies. Social Communications. Media Pedagogy"): "Features of the screen interpretation of the mythology of the 'evil' child within the horror genre in the 1990s-2000s" (Kostiuk, 2013e), "Genres of cinema" (Kostiuk, 2013a), "Contemporary genre cinema as a carrier of mythological principles" (Kostiuk, 2014), "Problems of genre definition of horror: Peculiarities of Differentiation and Multiple Interpretations" (Kostiuk, 2016f), "Screen Interpretation of the Monster Child Motif in the First Decade of the 2000s" (Kostiuk, 2016b), etc.

Publications in academic journals on audiovisual art ("Ukrainian Cinema: Past, Present, Prospects", "Prospects for the Development of Screen Arts in Ukraine", "Cultural and Artistic Environment: Creativity and Technology", "Chubasiv Readings", "Prospects for the Development of

Audiovisual Art", "Discursive Dimension of Contemporary Art: Dialogue of Cultures"): "The Impact of Screen Violence on Child and Adolescent Cruelty" (Kostiuk, 2011a), "Prospects for the Development of Horror in Ukraine" (Kostiuk, 2011c), "'Negative' Roles of Ivan Mykolaichuk" (Kostiuk, 2012c), "Violence as a Screen Technology" (Kostiuk, 2012b), "The Problem of Violence on the Contemporary TV Screen" (Kostiuk, 2012e), "Genre Cinema as a Means of Contemporary Mythmaking" (Kostiuk, 2013b), "On the Problem of the Genre Definition of Horror" (Kostiuk, 2015a), "The Italian Gothic Film" (Kostiuk, 2015b), "Categories of the Terrible and the Horrible in Horror" (Kostiuk, 2016d), "The Conservatism of the Horror Film: The Problem of Multiculturalism" (Kostiuk, 2016e), "On the Issue of Distinguishing the Genres of Thriller, Horror and Fantasy in Contemporary Cinema" (Kostiuk, 2016a), "Archetypal Fears in Contemporary Horror Film" (Kostiuk, 2017), "The Concept of the Evil-Bound Child in Japanese Neo-Classical Film" (Sichna, 2017b), etc.

The dissertation "The Image of the Child as a Central Character in Horror Films of the Second Half of the 20th – Early 21st Century" ("Sichna, 2018b") for the degree of Candidate of Arts in the speciality 17.00. 04 "Cinema, Television", Khrystyna Sichna (Batalina) prepared her thesis during her Master's degree ("Development of the Child's Image as a Negative Character within the Horror Genre") and postgraduate studies at the Department of Cinematography of the Institute of Screen Arts of the I. K. Karpenko-Kyiv National University of Theatre, Cinema and Television. Karpenko-Kary, and then brilliantly defended her thesis on 30 January 2019 at the Dissertation Council D 26.227.02 at the Rylsky Institute of Art

History, Folklore and Ethnology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine.

According to the information from the abstract ("Sichna, 2018a"), the official opponents of the thesis defence were well-known scholars in Ukraine: Doctor of Philology, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Journalism at the Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University Oleksandr Kholod and PhD in Art Studies, Associate Professor, Press Secretary of the NATO Representation to Ukraine Oksana Musiienko. Khrystyna Sichna's (Batalina's) thesis was supervised by Oleksandr Bezruchko, Doctor of Study of Art, Professor, Professor of the Department of Cinema and Television Arts at the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Vice-Rector for Research at the Kyiv University of Culture.

After defending her dissertation, Kh. Batalina continued to work on the above topics, significantly supplementing and expanding her previous research (as an example, we will cite only two articles in English published in the scientific professional journal of Ukraine on Audiovisual Art and Production: "On the Question of Differentiating the Main Philosophical and Aesthetic Categories of Horror Films" (Sichna, 2019) and "Violence in the Context of the History of World Cinema" (Batalina and Kostiuk, 2022).

As a logical conclusion of her work over more than a decade and a half, Khrystyna Batalina (2023) published a long-awaited individual monograph *The Child as the Embodiment of Evil in Horror Films of the Twentieth and Twenty-first Centuries* at the Kyiv University of Culture.

It should be noted that this book could have been published much earlier, but the COVID-19 pandemic and then the full-scale war in Ukraine delayed its release. However, despite all the troubles and dif-

faculties of our turbulent times, the management of the Kyiv University of Culture cares not only about the quality and stability of the educational process at this higher education establishment but also makes great efforts to encourage its employees to engage in scientific research, including the publication of articles and books. Khrystyna Batalina's monograph *The Child as the Embodiment of Evil in Horror Films of the Twentieth and Twenty-first Centuries* is a clear confirmation of this work.

The book under review by Khrystyna Batalina will help fill in the gaps in Ukrainian

film studies, focusing on the specifics of under-researched genres and types of films. The relevance of this study lies in its ability to highlight and analyse under-researched phenomena and trends in world and national cinema, as well as to make a significant contribution to the development of film studies in Ukraine.

In conclusion, I would like to recommend Khrystyna Friedrichivna Batalina's monograph *The Child as the Embodiment of Evil in Horror Films of the Twentieth and Twenty-First Centuries* to audiovisual art and production professionals and anyone interested in the history and theory of cinema.

Keywords: genre; horror; child; image; work; audiovisual art; cultural studies; character; evil

Ключові слова: жанр; жах; дитина; зображення; робота; аудіовізуальне мистецтво; культурологія; характер; зло

СПИСОК БІБЛІОГРАФІЧНИХ ПОСИЛАНЬ

- Баталіна, Х.Ф., 2023. *Дитина як втілення зла у фільмах жахів ХХ–ХХІ ст.* Київ: Видавничий центр КУК.
- Костюк, Х., 2011а. Вплив екранної жорстокості на дитячу та підліткову жорстокість. В: *Український кінематограф: минуле, сьогодні, перспективи*. Матеріали III круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 9 лютого 2011 р. Київ, с.58-61.
- Костюк, Х., 2011б. До історії створення та інтерпретацій одного з міфів сучасного кінематографічного «хоррору». *Студії мистецтвознавчі*, 1, с.99-109.
- Костюк, Х., 2011с. Перспективи розвитку хоррору в Україні. В: *Перспективи розвитку екранних мистецтв в Україні*. Матеріали III круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 17 листопада 2011 р. Київ, с.60-64.
- Костюк, Х., 2012а. До історії розвитку образу дитини у фільмах жахів. *Студії мистецтвознавчі*, 1, с.102-109.
- Костюк, Х., 2012б. Насильство як екранна технологія. В: *Культурно-мистецьке середовище: Творчість та технології*. Матеріали Шостої Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції. Київ, Україна, 8-9 листопада 2012 р. Київ, с.121-122.
- Костюк, Х., 2012с. «Негативні» ролі Івана Миколайчука. В: *Український кінематограф: минуле, сьогодні, перспективи*. Матеріали IV круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 10 лютого 2012 р. Київ, с.78-81.
- Костюк, Х., 2012д. Передумови для виникнення образу дитини як носія зла в сучасному українському та російському кінематографі. *Студії мистецтвознавчі*, 3, с.59-65.
- Костюк, Х., 2012е. Проблема насилля на сучасному телеекрані. В: *Перспективи розвитку екранних мистецтв в Україні*. Матеріали IV круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 6 листопада 2012 р. Київ, с.73-76.

- Костюк, Х., 2013а. Жанри кінематографу. В: *Актуальні питання екранної творчості*. Київ: КиМУ, Т. 2, с.71-88.
- Костюк, Х., 2013б. Жанровий кінематограф як засіб сучасної міфотворчості. В: *Перспективи розвитку екранних мистецтв в Україні*. Матеріали V круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 12 листопада 2013 р. Київ, с.74-78.
- Костюк, Х., 2013с. Екранні мистецтва як засіб формування сучасної міфологічної свідомості. *Студії мистецтвознавчі*, 3-4, с.14-22.
- Костюк, Х., 2013д. Містичні мотиви у творчості Юрія Ілленка. *Українознавчий альманах*, 11, с.202-204.
- Костюк, Х., 2013е. Особливості екранного трактування міфологеми «злої» дитини в рамках жанру хоррор у 1990–2000-них роках. В: *Кінознавство, культурологія та мистецтвознавство (соціально-комунікаційний аспект)*. Київ: КиМУ, с.279-307.
- Костюк, Х., 2014. Сучасне жанрове кіно як носій міфологічного начала. В: *Науково-практичні дослідження розвитку творчого процесу в різних видах мистецтва (кінематограф, телебачення, театр, медіа)*. Київ: КиМУ, Т. 2, с.231-244.
- Костюк, Х., 2015а. До проблеми жанрової дефініції хоррору. В: *Український кінематограф: минуле, сьогодення, перспективи*. Матеріали VII круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 5 лютого 2015 р. Київ, с.110-116.
- Костюк, Х., 2015б. Італійський готичний фільм. В: *Чубасівські читання*. Матеріали II круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 12 березня 2015 р. Київ, с.112-119.
- Костюк, Х., 2016а. До питання розмежування жанрів триллера, хорору і фантастики в сучасному кіномистецтві. В: *Дискурсивний вимір сучасного мистецтва: діалог культур*. Матеріали науково-теоретичної конференції. Київ, Україна, 30 листопада 2016 р. Київ, с.77-78.
- Костюк, Х., 2016б. Екранне трактування мотиву монструозної дитини у першому десятилітті 2000-х років. В: *Мистецтвознавство. Соціальні комунікації. Медіапедагогіка*. Київ: Видавничий центр КНУКіМ, Т. 2, с.97-111.
- Костюк, Х., 2016с. Італійський хоррор 60-х: ірраціональний жах на екрані. *Науковий вісник Київського національного університету театру, кіно і телебачення імені І. К. Карпенка-Карого*, 18, с.89-98.
- Костюк, Х., 2016д. Категорії страшного і жахливого у хоррорі. В: *Довженківські читання*. Матеріали круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 12 вересня 2016 р. Київ, с.43-45.
- Костюк, Х., 2016е. Консервативність фільму жахів: проблема мультикультуралізму. В: *Перспективи розвитку аудіовізуального мистецтва*. Матеріали круглого столу. Київ, Україна, 10 жовтня 2016 р. Київ, с.49-51.
- Костюк, Х., 2016ф. Проблеми жанрової дефініції хоррору: особливості розмежування та множинність трактування. В: *Генеza ідей і динаміка розвитку екранних мистецтв*. Київ, Т. 2, с.130-146.
- Костюк, Х., 2017. Архетипні страхи у сучасному фільмі жахів. В: *120-річчя українського кіно*. Матеріали Міжнародної наукової конференції. Київ, Україна, 20 грудня 2016 р. Київ, с.59-61.
- Січна, Х., 2017а. Концепція Зла в образі дитини: кінематографічні варіації у фільмах жахів. *European philosophical and historical discourse*, [online] 3 (4), pp.89-93. Доступно: <https://ephd.cz/wp-content/uploads/2017/ephd_2017_3_4/15.pdf> [Дата звернення 29 грудня 2023].

- Січна, Х., 2017b. Концепція пов'язаної зі злом дитини у японському неокайдані. В: *130-річчя від дня народження Івана Кавалерідзе. Матеріали Міжнародної наукової конференції*. Київ, Україна, 29 грудня 2017 р. Київ, с.54-56.
- Січна, Х.Ф., 2018a. *Образ дитини як центрального персонажа у фільмах жахів другої половини ХХ – початку ХХІ століття*. Автореферат кандидата мистецтвознавства. Інститут мистецтвознавства, фольклористики та етнології ім. М. Т. Рильського.
- Січна, Х.Ф., 2018b. *Образ дитини як центрального персонажа у фільмах жахів другої половини ХХ – початку ХХІ століття*. Кандидат наук. Інститут мистецтвознавства, фольклористики та етнології ім. М. Т. Рильського.
- Batalina, Kh. and Kostiuk, N., 2022. Violence in the Context of World Cinema History. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 5 (1), pp.54-63. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.5.1.2022.257178>
- Bezruchko, O., Gavran, I., Hrabarchuk, O., Kostiuk, N. and Kot, H., 2020. Ideological Concepts in the Cinematography of the Interwar Period. *Astra Salvensis*, 1, pp.669-690.
- Bezruchko, O. and Kachmar, N., 2021. The development of contemporary Ukrainian Cinema. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 4 (2), pp.208-216. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.2.2021.248680>
- Bezruchko, O. and Sukhin, M., 2023. Animated documentaries in modern cinematic art: specifics of production. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 6 (2), pp.241-251. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.6.2.2023.289310>
- Gavran, I., Levchenko, O. and Pasichnyk, O., 2021. Terror through screen images as a power discourse. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Arts and Production*, [e-journal] 4 (1), pp.28-34. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.1.2021.235066>
- Kotliar, S., Mykhalov, V. and Pereiaslavets, D., 2022. Cinematography and Modern Media. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 5 (1), pp.70-76 <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.5.1.2022.257181>
- Medvedieva, A. and Chernenko, S. 2021. Issues of the interview genre in contemporary media space. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Arts and Production*, [e-journal] 4 (1), pp.11-17. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.1.2021.235059>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Cherkasova, N., 2020. From "The Eleventh Year" to "The Man with a Movie Camera": conceptual search of Dziga Vertov. *Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie)*, [e-journal] 60 (3), pp.507-514. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2020.3.507>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Markhaichuk, N., 2020. Poetics of Ukrainian Film 'Earth': Oleksandr Dovzhenko's Conceptual Search. *Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie)*, [e-journal] 60 (4), pp.713-720. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2020.4.713>
- Myslavskiy, V. and Bezruchko, O., 2021. The Topic of the Soviet-Ukrainian War (1917–1921) in Ukrainian Cinematography of the 1920s. *Culture of Ukraine*, [e-journal] 73, pp.86-90. <https://doi.org/10.31516/2410-5325.073.12>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Kupriichuk, V., 2021. Formation of Ukrainian Newsreel and Documentary Cinema in 1923–1928. *Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie)*, [e-journal] 17 (4), pp.684-692. doi:10.13187/me.2021.4.684

Sichna, K., 2019. Concerning the Issue of the Horror Films Basic Philosophic and Aesthetic Categories Distinguishing. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 2 (1), pp.50-58. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.2.1.2019.170871>

REFERENCES

- Batalina, K. and Kostiuk, N., 2022. Violence in the Context of World Cinema History. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 5 (1), pp.54-63. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.5.1.2022.257178>
- Batalina, K.F., 2023. *Dytyna yak vtillennia zla u filmakh zhakhiv XX–XXI st.* [The child as the embodiment of evil in horror films of the 20th–21st centuries]. Kyiv: Vydavnychiy tsentr KUK.
- Bezruchko, O. and Kachmar, N., 2021. The Development of Contemporary Ukrainian Cinema. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 4 (2), pp.208-216. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.2.2021.248680>
- Bezruchko, O. and Sukhin, M., 2023. Animated Documentaries in Modern Cinematic Art: Specifics of Production. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 6 (2), pp.241-251. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.6.2.2023.289310>
- Bezruchko, O., Gavran, I., Hrabarchuk, O., Kostiuk, N. and Kot, H., 2020. Ideological Concepts in the Cinematography of the Interwar Period. *Astra Salvensis*, 1, pp.669-690.
- Gavran, I., Levchenko, O. and Pasichnyk, O., 2021. Terror Through Screen Images as a Power Discourse. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 4 (1), pp.28-34. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.1.2021.235066>
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2011a. Vplyv ekrannoi zhorstokosti na dytiachu ta pidlitkovu zhorstokist [The impact of screen violence on child and adolescent violence]. In: *Ukrainskyi kinematohraf: mynule, sohodennia, perspektyvy* [Ukrainian cinematography: past, present, prospects]. Collection of Proceedings of the 3rd round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 9 February, 2011. Kyiv, pp.58-61.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2011b. Do istorii stvorennia ta interpretatsii odnogo z mifiv suchasnoho kinematohrafichnoho "khorroru" [To the history of creation and interpretations of one of the myths of modern cinematic "horror"]. *Studii mystetstvoznavchi*, 1, pp.99-109.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2011c. Perspektyvy rozvytku khorroru v Ukraini [Prospects for the development of horror in Ukraine]. In: *Perspektyvy rozvytku ekrannykh mystetstv v Ukraini* [Prospects for the development of screen arts in Ukraine]. Collection of Proceedings of the 3rd round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 17 November, 2011. Kyiv, pp.60-64.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2012a. Do istorii rozvytku obrazu dytyny u filmakh zhakhiv [To the history of the development of the image of a child in horror films]. *Studii mystetstvoznavchi*, 1, pp.102-109.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2012b. Nasylstvo yak ekranna tekhnolohiia [Violence as screen technology]. In: *Kulturno-mystetske seredovyshe: Tvorchist ta tekhnolohii* [Cultural and artistic environment: Creativity and technologies]. Collection of Proceedings of the Sixth International Scientific and Practical Conference. Kyiv, Ukraine, 8-9 November, 2012. Kyiv, pp.121-122.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2012c. "Nehatyvni" roli Ivana Mykolaichuka ["Negative" roles of Ivan Mykolaichuk]. In: *Ukrainskyi kinematohraf: mynule, sohodennia, perspektyvy* [Ukrainian cinematography: past, present, prospects]. Collection of Proceedings of the IV round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 10 February, 2012. Kyiv, pp.78-81.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2012d. Peredumovy dlia vynyknennia obrazu dytyny yak nosiia zla v suchasnomu ukrainskomu ta rosiiskomu kinematohrafi [Prerequisites for the emergence of the image of a child as a bearer of evil in modern Ukrainian and Russian cinema]. *Studii mystetstvoznavchi*, 3, pp.59-65.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2012e. Problema nasyllia na suchasnomu teleekrani [The problem of violence on the modern TV screen]. In: *Perspektyvy rozvytku ekrannykh mystetstv v Ukraini* [Prospects for the development of screen arts in Ukraine]. Collection of Proceedings of the IV round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 6 November, 2012. Kyiv, pp.73-76.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2013a. Zhanry kinematohrafu [Genres of cinematography]. In: *Aktualni pytannia ekrannoi tvorchosti* [Current issues of screen creativity]. Kyiv: KyMU, Vol. 2, pp.71-88.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2013b. Zhanrovyi kinematohraf yak zasib suchasnoi mifotvorchosti [Genre cinema as a means of modern mythmaking]. In: *Perspektyvy rozvytku ekrannykh mystetstv v Ukraini* [Prospects for the development of screen arts in Ukraine]. Collection of Proceedings of the V round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 12 November, 2013. Kyiv, pp.74-78.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2013c. Ekranni mystetstva yak zasib formuvannia suchasnoi mifolohichnoi svidomosti [Screen arts as a means of forming modern mythological consciousness]. *Studii mystetstvoznavchi*, 3-4, pp.14-22.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2013d. Mistychni motyvy u tvorchosti Yurii Illienka [Mystical motifs in the work of Yuriy Illenko]. *Ukrainoznavchyi almanakh*, 11, pp.202-204.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2013e. Osoblyvosti ekrannoho traktuvannia mifolohemy «zloi» dytyny v ramkakh zhanru khorror u 1990-2000-nykh rokakh [Peculiarities of the on-screen treatment of the myth of the "evil" child within the framework of the horror genre in the 1990s and 2000s]. In: *Kinoznavstvo, kulturolohiia ta mystetstvoznavstvo (sotsialno-komunikatsiinyi aspekt)* [Film studies, cultural studies and art studies (social and communication aspect)]. Kyiv: KyMU, pp.279-307.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2014. Suchasne zhanrove kino yak nosii mifolohichnoho nachala. [Modern genre cinema as a carrier of mythological principle]. In: *Naukovo-praktychni doslidzhennia rozvytku tvorchoho protsesu v riznykh vydakh mystetstva (kinematohraf, telebachennia, teatr, media)* [Scientific and practical studies of the development of the creative process in various forms of art (cinematography, television, theater, media)]. Kyiv: KyMU, Vol. 2, pp.231-244.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2015a. Do problemy zhanrovoi definitsii khorroru [To the problem of genre definition of horror]. In: *Ukrainskyi kinematohraf: mynule, sohodennia, perspektyvy* [Ukrainian cinematography: past, present, prospects]. Collection of Proceedings of the VII round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 5 February, 2015. Kyiv, pp.110-116.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2015b. Italiiskyi hotychnyi film [Italian gothic film]. In: *Chubasivski chytannia* [Chubasiv readings]. Collection of Proceedings of the II round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 12 March, 2015. Kyiv, pp.112-119.

Kostiuk, Kh., 2016a. Do pytannia rozmezhuвання zhanriv trylleru, khororu i fantastyky v suchasnomu kinomystetstvi [To the issue of distinguishing the genres of thriller, horror and fantasy in modern cinema]. In: *Dyskursyvnyi vymir suchasnoho mystetstva: dialoh kultur*

- [Discursive dimension of modern art: dialogue of cultures]. Collection of Proceedings of the scientific theoretical conference. Kyiv, Ukraine, 30 November, 2016. Kyiv, pp.77-78.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2016b. Ekranne traktuvannia motyvu monstroznoi dytyny u pershomu desiatylitti 2000-kh rokiv [On-screen interpretation of the motif of the monstrous child in the first decade of the 2000s]. In: *Mystetstvoznavstvo. Sotsialni komunikatsii. Mediapedahohika* [Art studies. Social communications. Media pedagogy]. Kyiv: Vydavnychi tsentr KNUKiM, Vol. 2, pp.97-111.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2016c. Italiiskyi khorrор 60-kh: irratsionalnyi zhakh na ekranі [Italian horror of the 60s: irrational horror on the screen]. *Naukovyi visnyk Kyivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu teatru, kino i telebachennia imeni I. K. Karpenka-Karoho*, 18, pp.89-98.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2016d. Katehорії strashnoho і zhakhlyvoho u khorrорі [Categories of scary and terrible in horror]. In: *Dovzhenkivski chytannia* [Dovzhenki's readings]. Collection of Proceedings of the round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 12 September, 2016. Kyiv, pp.43-45.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2016e. Konservatyvnist filmu zhakhiv: problema multykulturalizmu [The Conservatism of the Horror Film: The Problem of Multiculturalism]. In: *Perspektyvy rozvytku audiovizualnoho mystetstva* [Prospects for the development of audiovisual art]. Collection of Proceedings of the round table. Kyiv, Ukraine, 10 October, 2016. Kyiv, pp.49-51.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2016f. Problemy zhanrovi defynitsii khorrору: osoblyvosti rozmezhuвання ta mnozhyhnist traktuvannia [Problems of genre definition of horror: peculiarities of demarcation and multiplicity of interpretation]. In: *Heneza idei i dynamika rozvytku ekrannykh mystetstv* [The genesis of ideas and the dynamics of the development of screen arts]. Kyiv, Vol. 2, pp.130-146.
- Kostiuk, Kh., 2017. Arkhetypni strakhy u suchasnomu filmi zhakhiv [Archetypal fears in the modern horror film]. In: *120-richchia ukrainskoho kino* [120th anniversary of Ukrainian cinema]. Collection of Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. Kyiv, Ukraine, 20 December, 2016. Kyiv, pp.59-61.
- Kotliar, S., Mykhalov, V. and Pereiaslavets, D., 2022. Cinematography and Modern Media. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 5(1), pp.70-76. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.5.1.2022.257181>
- Medvedieva, A. and Chernenko, S., 2021. Issues of the Interview Genre in Contemporary Media Space. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 4(1), pp.11-17. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.4.1.2021.235059>
- Myslavskiy, V. and Bezruchko, O., 2021. The topic of the Soviet-Ukrainian war (1917–1921) in Ukrainian cinematography of the 1920s. *Culture of Ukraine*, [e-journal] 73, pp.86-90. <https://doi.org/10.31516/2410-5325.073.12>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Cherkasova, N., 2020. From "The Eleventh Year" to "The Man with a Movie Camera": conceptual search of Dziga Vertov. *Media Education*, [e-journal] 60(3), pp.507-514. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2020.3.507>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Kupriichuk V., 2021. Formation of Ukrainian Newsreel and Documentary Cinema in 1923-1928. *Media Education*, [e-journal] 17(4), pp.684-692. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2021.4.684>
- Myslavskiy, V., Chmil, G., Bezruchko, O. and Markhaichuk, N., 2020. Poetics of Ukrainian Film "Earth": Oleksandr Dovzhenko's Conceptual Search. *Media Education*, [e-journal] 60(4), pp.713-720. <https://doi.org/10.13187/me.2020.4.713>

Sichna, K. F., 2018a. *Obraz dytyny yak tsentralnoho personazha u filmakh zhakhiv druhoi polovyny XX – pochatku XXI stolittia* [The image of a child as the central character in Horror Movies of the 2nd part of 20th – the 1st part of 21st centuries]. Abstract of the Ph.D. Instytut mystetstvoznavstva, folklorystyky ta etnologii im. M. T. Rylskoho Natsionalnoi akademii nauk Ukrainy.

Sichna, K. F., 2018b. *Obraz dytyny yak tsentralnoho personazha u filmakh zhakhiv druhoi polovyny XX – pochatku XXI stolittia* [The image of a child as the central character in Horror Movies of the 2nd part of 20th – the 1st part of 21st centuries]. Ph.D. Instytut mystetstvoznavstva, folklorystyky ta etnologii im. M. T. Rylskoho Natsionalnoi akademii nauk Ukrainy.

Sichna, K., 2019. Concerning the Issue of the Horror Films Basic Philosophic and Aesthetic Categories Distinguishing. *Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Audiovisual Art and Production*, [e-journal] 2 (1), pp.50-58. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2617-2674.2.1.2019.170871>

Sichna, Kh., 2017a. Kontseptsiiia Zla v obrazi dytyny: kinematohrafichni variatsii u filmakh zhakhiv [The Concept of Evil as a Child: Cinematic Variations in Horror Films]. *European philosophical and historical discourse*, [online] 3 (4), pp.89-93. Available at: <https://ephd.cz/wp-content/uploads/2017/ephd_2017_3_4/15.pdf> [Accessed 29 December 2023].

Sichna, Kh., 2017b. Kontseptsiiia poviazanoi zi zlom dytyny u yaponskomu neokaidani [The concept of the evil child in Japanese Neokaidan]. In: *130-richchia vid dnia narodzhennia Ivana Kavaleridze* [130th anniversary of the birth of Ivan Kavaleridze]. Collection of Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. Kyiv, Ukraine, 29 December, 2017. Kyiv, pp.54-56.

